

Introducing Powder2Power

Total budget: €5,884M
EU contribution: €5,274M

Duration: 48 months
(10/2023 – 09/2027)

Consortium:
9 partners, 6 EU countries

Technology: Fluidized
particle-driven CSP

Powder2Power is an EU-funded project aiming to demonstrate, in an operational environment (TRL7*) and at a megawatt scale, an original and cost-effective particle-driven CSP technology, applicable to both electricity and industrial heat production.

Expected Impacts

Technology

Improve CSP plant efficiency and reliability through innovative solar technology, including prototype testing and engineering solutions

Science

Strengthen European research and expertise in renewable energy, fostering international collaboration and innovation

Society & Environment

Enhance environmental sustainability and EU industrial competitiveness by reducing CO₂ emissions and creating jobs in the renewable energy sector

* Technology readiness level 7: system prototype demonstration in operational environment

Interested in collaborating, partnering,
or learning more?
Contact us and get involved!

www.powder2power-project.eu

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MW-scale fluidized particle-driven CSP prototype demonstration

Concentrated Solar Technology for More Efficient and Cost-Effective Power and Industrial Heat generation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101122347.

Concept and Vision at a glance

Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) plays a key role in green energy production. While molten salt is the leading heat transfer medium, **particle suspensions offer the potential for even higher operating temperatures in CSP plants, supporting more efficient power cycles**, like the sCO₂ cycle, which operates at 700-750°C with 50 per cent efficiency.

Powder2Power aims to advance the future of CSP with an innovative 2 MWth particle-driven CSP prototype. Building on the EU-funded Next-CSP project (H2020, GA n°727762), the project focuses on optimizing the technology by integrating a ~90m vertical particle transport system and validating electricity-powered particle superheated thermal storage, simulating a high-temperature hybrid CSP-PV concept.

The project **primary goal is to assess the techno-economic viability and sustainability of the concept for commercial use**, with a focus on a 30-60 MWe power plant. Scaling up will be based on validated models and real operational data.

This system will be tested at the Themis solar tower in Targassonne, France.

Objectives

Innovative Demonstration

Showcasing cutting-edge, cost-effective CSP components and systems at a megawatt scale in an operational environment

Sustainable Energy Integration

Developing a particle-to-sCO₂ heat exchanger to enhance high-capacity energy storage

Operational Efficiency

Reducing O&M costs by integrating a particle-based storage solution and improving the sun-to-power cycle efficiency by approximately 12%

Renewable Energy Advancement

Supporting renewable energy growth by increasing the share of variable renewables through efficient particle-based thermal energy storage

Consortium

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BUILD TO ZERO

